

Subject 1: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis on Risk Factors for Sporadic Food-Borne Illnesses

Hepatitis A infection

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The quality assessment stage was passed by 78 primary studies investigating risk factors for sporadic infection with hepatitis A, which were conducted between 1985 and 2013. From these, seventeen studies investigated exposures in children, fifty-eight in the mixed population, two studies in drug-user adults, and one study in immunodeficient individuals. These primary studies provided 426 ORs categorised for meta-analysis, being 70% of the meta-analytical data produced by observational studies from Italy (66 ORs), USA (61 ORs), Brazil (41 ORs), Korea (39 ORs), UK (37 ORs), France (30 ORs) and China (24 ORs). Seventy-four studies (~94%) employed an unmatched experimental design and produced a total of 335 ORs. From these, 189 reported or computed ORs were not adjusted by any confounder (i.e., crude ORs), while the others were adjusted by using either unconditional logistic regressions (136 ORs) or Mantel-Haenzel method (10 ORs). On the other hand, only five studies (~6%) employed a matched experimental design, providing for meta-analysis a total of 91 ORs. Most of them were estimated by conditional logistic regression (47) and Mantel-Haenzel method (29). After methodological quality assessment, ten primary studies were marked as being possibly affected by selection or data analysis bias, which yielded a total of 50 potentially-biased ORs. Within the pathways of transmission, the largest share (60%) of data came from exposures related with environment (143 ORs) and person-to-person contagion (110 ORs).

In the mixed population, the most important global risk factors for hepatitis A infection were travel (overall OR=3.15; 95% CI: 2.36 – 4.19), host-specific factors (overall OR=2.20; 95% CI: 1.34 – 3.61) and food consumption (overall OR=2.12; 95% CI: 1.45 – 3.10), mainly represented by seafood (overall OR=2.03; 95% CI: 1.25 – 3.30). In children, the top two global risk factors were host-specific (overall 3.96; 95% CI: 1.54 – 10.14) and person-to-person contagion (overall OR=3.20; 95% CI: 1.35 – 7.59). However, person-to-person transmission in the mixed (overall OR=1.77; 95% CI: 1.40 – 2.22) and the susceptible

population (overall OR=1.80; 95% CI: 0.96 – 3.39), was not as a strong determinant of disease as it was found to be in children; yet the risk associated to person-to-person transmission in the mixed and susceptible population was rather comparable to keeping poor hygiene habits (overall OR=1.77; 95% CI: 1.04 – 3.02). As a whole, the animal contact pathways (overall OR=1.63; 95% CI: 1.24 – 2.14 in the mixed population) and the environmental pathways (overall OR=1.61; 95% CI: 1.38 – 1.90 in the mixed population; and overall OR=1.64; 95% CI: 1.26 – 2.13 in children) bore discernably lower risk of acquiring hepatitis A infection than travel or seafood consumption.

Among the disaggregated pathways of exposure to hepatitis A, non-specific seafood (overall OR=7.24; 95% CI: 5.28 – 9.93 in the mixed population) and eating meals from street vendor (overall OR=7.89; 95% CI: 4.26 – 14.60 in children) turned out to pose the greatest risk of infection, followed by international travel (overall OR=4.26; 95% CI: 2.70 – 6.74) and consumption of vegetables (overall OR=2.79; 95% CI: 0.86 – 9.02). In the mixed population, having a history of hepatitis/jaundice, hypercholesterolemia (i.e., other medical conditions; overall OR=2.65; 95% CI: 1.52 – 4.62) was as important a risk factor for acquiring hepatitis A infection as the consumption of molluscs (overall OR=2.50; 95% CI: 1.39 – 4.51) and domestic travel (overall OR=2.33; 95% CI: 1.45 – 3.73). Interestingly, the exposures related to day care, be it either adults working at day care centre (overall OR=1.93; 95% CI: 1.18 – 3.18) or children attending day care (overall OR=1.68; 95% CI: 1.02 – 2.75) bore a level of risk comparable to those of being exposed to waste, sewage or lack of sanitation (overall OR=1.88; 95% CI: 1.47 – 2.39 in the mixed population; and overall OR=1.65; 95% CI: 1.41 – 1.92 in children) and living on a farm (overall OR=1.86; 95% CI: 1.46 – 2.37 in the mixed population; and overall OR=1.36; 95% CI: 0.97 – 1.92 in children). Thus, day care is a significant environmental pathway of transmission of hepatitis A.

In children, as opposed to the mixed population, person-to-person contagion (overall OR=3.20; 95% CI: 1.35 – 7.59) was a more important source of hepatitis A infection than international travel (overall OR=2.27; 95% CI: 1.43 – 3.60), whereas suffering from other medical condition bore, at least on average, a similar level of risk (overall OR=2.62; 95% CI: 0.68 – 10.11) as in the mixed population. On meta-analysis, children drinking bottled water (overall OR=2.00; 95% CI: 1.27 – 3.13) could be as exposed to hepatitis A as drinking untreated water (overall OR=1.81; 95% CI: 1.22 – 2.69). Other significant routes of transmission of hepatitis A in the mixed population were: contact with garden and soil (overall OR=1.76; 95% CI: 1.05 – 2.95), consumption of non-specific seafood/meat outside the home (overall OR=1.69; 95% CI: 1.05 – 2.74) and drinking untreated water (overall OR=1.22; 95% CI: 1.07 – 1.38); while minor (or not statistically proven) factors for acquiring the disease were: suffering from a chronic disease (overall OR=1.48; 95% CI: 0.76 – 2.89), exposure to recreational water (overall OR=1.08; 95% CI: 0.68 – 1.70) and consumption of crustaceans (overall OR=0.97; 95% CI: 0.76 – 1.23).

3. Results

3.10 Hepatitis A

3.10.1 Descriptive statistics

In the systematic review of risk factors for human infection with *Hepatitis A*, a total of 1624 clean bibliographic sources were identified using appropriate keywords in five bibliographic search engines, from which 168 case-control and cohort studies passed the full assessment for eligibility (Figure 1). From these, ninety fully-documented case-control studies investigated the source(s) of outbreaks and were kept in the JabRef file as their data can be readily extracted. Meta-analysis was undertaken on data either extracted or calculated from 78 primary studies – cohort and case-control studies – focusing on sporadic disease (Figure 1). These published studies were conducted in years spanning from 1985 and 2013. Table 1 compiles a list of the primary studies along with their main features. The eligible studies jointly provided 426 odds-ratios categorised for meta-analysis. A total of 231 ORs were retrieved from 35 case-control studies performed before the year 2000, while 195 ORs were excerpted from 43 case-control studies performed after 2000. Meta-analytical data were obtained from primary studies conducted in 31 countries, although studies from only 7 countries generated ~70% of the ORs retrieved. These were: Italy (66 ORs), USA (61 ORs), Brazil (41 ORs), Korea (39 ORs), UK (37 ORs), France (30 ORs) and China (24 ORs) (Figure 2, top).

Primary studies investigated risk factors in different types of population, namely children (17 studies), mixed population (58 studies) and susceptible population (3 studies), which included immunodeficient individuals (one study: Brunet et al., 2005) and drug-users (2 studies: Collier et al., 2015 and Luquero et al., 2009). Whenever the amount of data allowed, separate meta-analyses were adjusted on the mixed population (322 ORs) and the combined children (89 ORs) and susceptible (15 ORs) population (Figure 2, bottom left). Only five case-control studies employed a matched experimental design and produced a total of 91 categorised ORs, which represented 21.3% of the data. Of these, 22 ORs were computed in multivariate analysis whereas 69 were obtained in univariate analysis. ORs from matched designs were mostly estimated by conditional logistic regression (47) and Mantel-Haenzel (29), and a few estimated by chi-square (12) and unconditional logistic (3 ORs).

From the 74 studies that applied an unmatched design, a total of 335 ORs were extracted or calculated, which constituted 78.6% of the meta-analytical data. A total of 250 ORs were computed in univariate analysis while 85 in multivariate analysis. Most of the ORs from unmatched designs were estimated using chi-square (189) and UL (136) whilst only 10 ORs were MH-estimates adjusted by a confounding variable. Bringing together the matched and unmatched designs, 255 ORs (60% of the data) were not adjusted by any confounder (crude ORs), while 171ORs (40%) were adjusted using either MH or logistic regressions (Figure 3).

Figure 1. Flow chart of literature search for case-control or cohort studies of hepatitis A infection

*Records kept in JabRef with PDFs files annexed

Figure 2. Distribution of the number of odds-ratios (y-axis) extracted from case-control studies of sporadic hepatitis A by country (top left), population type (bottom left) and pathway of exposure (bottom right)

Figure 3. Pie-diagrams of the number of odds-ratios extracted from case-control and cohort studies of sporadic hepatitis A infection by design (top left), analysis type (top right), model type (middle left), odds-ratio type (middle right), study period cut off year 2000 (bottom left) and type of diagnosis test (bottom right). ELISA test can target IgG, IgM or both

Table 1. Characteristics of the 78 primary studies investigating risk factors for acquiring sporadic hepatitis A included in the meta-analysis

Study	Country	Study period	Population	Design	Analysis & model	# ill/ non-ill	Quality #ORs/Removed*
Akbar et al. 1996	Indonesia	Jan-Jun1994	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	861 ill 126 non-ill	Good 4
Almeida et al.2001	Brazil	Jun-Dec 1997	Mixed	Unmatched	Multi-UL	539 ill 1617 non-ill	Poor 5
Ballesteros et al. 1996	Spain	Mar-Jun 1994	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	68 ill 80 non-ill	Good 3
Barros et al. 1999	Portugal	1998	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	186 ill 481 non-ill	Good 3
Bawazir et al. 2010	Yemen	Apr-Jul 2005	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	467 ill 72 non-ill	Good 6
Benbrik et al. 2000	France	Mar-May 1995	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	850 ill 383 non-ill	Good 8
Bialek et al. 2011	USA	1994-2000	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Uni-UL	63 ill 668 non-ill	Good 17
Braga et al. 2009	Brazil	Mar-April 2005	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	1118 ill 381 non-ill	Good 5
Brannen et al. 2016	USA	Jan 2010-Dec 2014	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-UL	162 ill 774 non-ill	Good 1
Brugha et al. 1998	UK	1998	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-UL Uni-Chi	79 ill 149 non-ill	Good 2
Brunet et al. 2005	France	May-Dec 2001	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	112 ill 42 non-ill	Good 6
Cadilhac P. and Roudot-Thoraval F. 1996	France	Nov-Dec 1993	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	126 ill 99 non-ill	Good 3
Chironna et al. 2012	Italy	2008-2009	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	98 ill 17 non-ill	Poor 5
Cho et al. 2011	Korea	Jun 2008 - Dec 2009	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	854 ill 132 non-ill	Good 2
Chodick et al. 2003	Israel	2003	Mixed	Unmatched	Multi-UL	544 ill 383 non-ill	Good 2
Ciccozzi et al. 2002	Italy	1996-2000	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	8258 ill 700 non-ill	Poor 8
Collier et al. 2015	USA	2009-2010	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	195 ill 325 non-ill	Good 3
Corona et al. 1999	Italy	Jan-Dec 1997	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	178 ill 108 non-ill	Good 4
De Alencar et al. 2008	Brazil	2004-2005	Children	Unmatched	Uni-UL	320 ill 383 non-ill	Good 18
Delarocque et al. 2012	Egypt	2002-2007	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	68 ill 17 non-ill	Poor 2/3
De Serres et al. 2002	Canada	Jan1997-Nov1999	Mixed	Unmatched	Multi-UL	78 ill 689 non-ill	Good 3
Divizia et al. 2008	Italy	2007	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	51 ill 87 non-ill	Good 1

Dominguez et al. 2007	Spain	2002	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	940 ill 352 non-ill	Good 1
Dounias G. and Rachiotis G. 2006	UK	Oct 2004 - Apr 2005	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	72 ill 79 non-ill	Good 4
Duggirala et al. 2005	USA	Aug 1999 - Apr 2000	Mixed	Matched	Uni-MH Multi-CL	72 ill 144 non-ill	Good 5/1
El-Gilany et al. 2010	Saudi Arabia	Feb 2006 - Jan 2007	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	321 ill 629 non-ill	Good 6
Escobedo-Meléndez et al. 2012	Mexico	2005 - 2009	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	107 ill 30 non-ill	Good 4/2
Faillon et al. 2013	France	Jun 2008 - Jul 2009	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	20 ill 410 non-ill	Good 3
Gammie A.J. and Wyn-Jones A.P. 1997	UK	1995	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	29 ill 205 non-ill	Poor 1
Gil et al. 1999	Spain	Jun 1996 - Jan 1997	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-MH	119 ill 195 non-ill	Good 2
Grzeszczuk et al. 2003	Poland	1999	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	333 ill 169 non-ill	Good 1
Halicioğlu et al. 2012	Turkey	Apr-Dec 2009	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	199 ill 544 non-ill	Good 6
Hennessey et al. 2009	USA	Apr 1999-Mar 2000	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	435 ill 283 non-ill	Good 2
Hellara et al. 2014	Tunisia	Jan 2004- Dec 2005	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	36 ill 27 non-ill	Poor 1
Heriberto et al. 2002	Peru	Apr-Dec 2000	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	257 ill 13 non-ill	Good 6
Houcine et al. 2013	Tunisia	Set 2007- Jun 2008	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	54 ill 148 non-ill	Good 4
Hyams et al. 1999	Sudan	Jan 1987- May 1988	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	27 ill 80 non-ill	Good 2
Junquera et al. 2004	Spain	Apr-Sep 2002	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	231 ill 326 non-ill	Good 1
Karimi et al. 2016	Iran	2013	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	445 ill 46 non-ill	Good 2
Kim et al. 2011	Korea	Jan 2000-Feb 2010	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	30 ill 419 non-ill	Poor 4
Kotwal et al. 2014	India	2010-2011	Mixed	Unmatched	Multi-UL	3974 ill 201 non-ill	Good 5
Lagarde et al. 1995	France	Oct 1992- Jun 1993	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-MH Multi-UL	152 ill 764 non-ill	Good 10
Letaief et al. 2005	Tunisia	Apr 2002	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	143 ill 955 non-ill	Good 4
Levin et al. 2000	Israel	Nov 1996-Apr 1997	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	173 ill 27 non-ill	Good 1/1
Lin et al. 2005	Taiwan	2003	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	4 ill 281 non-ill	Good 1
Lopalco et al. 2005	Italy	1989-2001	Mixed	Matched	Multi-UL Uni-CL	207 ill 207 non-ill	Good 15

				Unmatched	Multi-UL	192 ill 193 non-ill	
Luquero et al.2009	Spain	Apr 2001- Dec2003	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	338 ill 615 non-ill	Good 6
Maguire et al.1995	UK	Jul1990- Jun1991	Mixed	Matched	Uni-CL Multi-CL	1230 ill 993 non-ill	Good 30/1
Mantovani et al.2015	Brazil	Jen-Feb 2011	Children	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	62 ill 250 non-ill	Good 8
Mausezahl et al.1996	China	Apr-Aug 1994	Mixed	Matched	Uni-Chi Multi-CL	100 ill 100 non-ill	Good 16
Masia et al. 2004	Italy	Nov1999-May 2000	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	13 ill 519 non-ill	Poor 2
Mele et al.1997	Italy	1985-1994	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	6408 ill 8143 non-ill	Poor 6
Montuori et al. 2009	Italy	Jan 2006- Dec 2007	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	1069 ill 110 non-ill	Good 2
Mostafavi et al.2016	Iran	2009-2010	Children	Unmatched	Multi-UL	1595 ill 897 non-ill	Good 1
Muecke 2002	Canada	2001	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	175 ill 317 non-ill	Good 5
Nielsen et al. 2012	Denmark	2000-2010	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	42 ill 1188 non-ill	Good 7
Nubling et al. 2002	Germany	2001	Adult	Unmatched	Multi-UL	143 ill 368 non-ill	Good 2
Peled et al. 2002	Israel	1995-1996	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	305 ill 9 non-ill	Good 5
Quaglio et al. 2008	Kosovo	Jan 2005-Mar 2005	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	1138 ill 147 non-ill	Good 6
Queiroz et al. 1995	Brazil	May 1991- April 1992	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	216 ill 94 non-ill	Good 3
Rachiotis et al. 2016	Greece	Jan-Aug 2008	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	48 ill 85 non-ill	Good 1
Rachiotis et al. 2002	Greece	2007-2008	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	90 ill 118 non-ill	Good 4
Rafeey M. and Sharan M.2014	Iran	Apr 2012- 2013	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	83 ill 169 non-ill	Good 1
Ramezani et al.2011	Iran	2008	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	327ill 18 non-ill	Good 1
Redlinger et al. 1997	Mexico	Jan-Jun1996	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	95 ill 466 non-ill	Good 7
Sagliocca et al. 1995	Italy	Jan-May1990	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	193 ill 231 non-ill	Good 7
Seo et al. 2013	Korea	2007-2009	Mixed	Matched	Uni-MH Multi-CL	786 ill 770 non-ill	Good 33
Sonder et al. 2004	Netherlands	Jan 1996-Dec 2000	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	446 ill 343 non-ill	Good 5

Taylor et al. 1995	SouthAfrica	1992	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	253 ill 531 non-ill	Good 3
Termorshuizen et al. 2000	Netherlands	Oct 1995-Dec 1996	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-UL	6483 ill 884 non-ill	Good 3
Tosti et al. 2008	Italy	2001-2006	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	5384 ill 3306 non-ill	Poor 16
Vatev et al. 2011	Bulgaria	Oct 2006-Dec 2007	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	105 ill 100 non-ill	Good 1
Venczel et al. 2003	USA	1999	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	196 ill 335 non-ill	Good 10
Vitral et al. 2014	Brazil	Mar-Apr 2004	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	329 ill 68 non-ill	Good 2
Weldon et al. 2000	USA	Mar1996- Apr 1997	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	123 ill 235 non-ill	Good 8
Weinberg et al. 2004	USA	Jun 1998-Aug 2000	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	132 ill 354 non-ill	Good 11
Wu et al. 2015	China	Dec 2010-Oct 2012	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Uni-UL	6 ill 709 non-ill	Good 8
Zhu et al. 2000	USA	2000	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	205 ill 186 non-ill	Good 4

(*) Number of ORs removed for having mean values below 0.5, however there was no data for breastfeeding

During methodological quality assessment, potential for selection bias was assigned to ten case-control studies. In Chironna et al. (2012), Ciccozzi et al. (2002), Hellara et al. (2014), Mele et al. (1997), Kim et al. (2011) and Tosti et al. (2008), the “controls/non-ill people” were affected by hepatitis B or C, while in Delarocque et al. (2012) and Massia et al. (2004), the controls were hepatitis E positive. In Gammie and Wyn-Jones (1997), the odds of acquiring hepatitis A from “being a surfer” was compared against “being a windsurfer”, instead of “not being a surfer”, whereas in Almeida et al. (2001) the association estimates were obtained by adjusting a generalised model with a complementary loglog function. The 50 ORs extracted from the studies above were marked as having potential for bias, and their influence on the meta-analysed OR estimates was appraised by means of the Cook’s distance. With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused much more on the multiple pathways of transmission (317 ORs) than on host-specific factors (37 ORs) or travel (72 ORs). None of the primary studies investigated whether breastfeeding could exert any protective effect against hepatitis A. Within the pathways of transmission, the largest share of data came from exposures related with environment (143 ORs) and person-to-person contagion (110 ORs) (Figure 2, bottom right). General information on the distribution of the number of ORs available for meta-analysis is presented in Figure 3 by study design, type of analysis, model, type of odds-ratio, study period and potential for bias status.

3.10.2 *Meta-analysis for host-specific risk factors and travel-, environment-, animal-, food-related and person-to-person pathways of transmission*

Study period was not found to be influential in any of the meta-analytical data partitions. Thus, it can be said that, in earlier years, the association measures between hepatitis A and the pathways of transmission commonly considered as potential sources of disease did not differ significantly from those quantified in the most recent years.

Table 2A. Meta-analyses of travel as a risk factor for acquiring hepatitis A infection by geographical region for the mixed population (n=60 ORs) and the combined children (n=10) and susceptible (n=2) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	1.159	0.625	3	[-0.066 – 2.384]	0.064
North America	1.685	0.303	7	[1.092 – 2.278]	<.0001
North Europe	1.497	0.340	15	[0.830 – 2.163]	<.0001
West Europe	0.882	0.157	35	[0.574 – 1.190]	<.0001
Children/suscep					
Asia	0.350	1.075	2	[-1.756 – 2.456]	0.745
North America	0.708	0.354	4	[0.014 – 1.401]	0.045
South America	0.596	0.409	3	[-0.205 – 1.397]	0.144
West Europe	1.012	0.437	3	[0.157 – 1.868]	0.020

Table 2B. Meta-analyses of travel as a risk factor for acquiring hepatitis A infection in the mixed (n=60) and the combined children (n=10) and susceptible (n=2) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	All Travel	1.146	0.146	60	[0.860 – 1.433]	<.0001
(23 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Abroad	1.450 ^b	0.233	52	[0.993 – 1.908]	<.0001
	Inside	0.844 ^a	0.241	8	[0.372 – 1.317]	0.001
	Before 2000					0.977
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1660	QE(df=58)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	1.4913	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0000			0.842
	Points removed	0				

Children/ Suscep (7 stud)	All Travel*	0.735	0.230	12	[0.283 – 1.187]	0.001
	Fixed effects					
	Abroad	0.819 ^b	0.236	11	[0.356 – 1.281]	0.001
	Before 2000					0.275
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2234	QE(df=10)			
	s^2 (residual)	0.5799	p<.0001			
	Publication bias	0.0028	0.0009			0.002
	Points removed	0				

(*) 11 ORs for Travel Abroad and 1 OR for Travel Inside

Figure 4. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of travel as a risk factor for hepatitis A infection in the mixed (left) and the combined children and susceptible (right) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 3A. Meta-analyses of host-specific factors for hepatitis A infection by region for the mixed population (n=20) and the combined children (n=3) and susceptible (n=2) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	1.001	0.333	11	[0.348 – 1.654]	0.003
North America	0.412	0.713	4	[-0.985 – 1.809]	0.563
West Europe	0.561	0.425	5	[-0.272 – 1.394]	0.187
Children*/Suscep					
Asia	0.962	0.689	3	[-0.390 – 2.314]	0.163
West Europe	1.766	0.668	2	[0.457 – 3.075]	0.008

(*) No breastfeeding data

Table 3B. Meta-analysis of host-specific factors for hepatitis A infection in the mixed (n=20) and the combined children (n=3) and susceptible (n=2) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	All host-specific	0.789	0.253	20	[0.293 – 1.285]	0.002
(10 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Chronic	0.392 ^a	0.342	10	[-0.279 – 1.062]	0.253
	Other med	0.974 ^b	0.284	10	[0.416 – 1.531]	0.001
	Before 2000					0.424
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.3329	QE(df=18)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.4726	p<.0001		p=0.002	
	Publication bias	0.0007	0.0005			0.217
	Points removed	0				
Children/ suscep	All host-specific	1.377	0.480	5	[0.434 – 2.317]	0.004
(3 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Immuno in susc	1.766 ^b	0.668	2	[0.457 – 3.074]	0.008
	Other med in child	0.962 ^a	0.689	3	[-0.390 – 2.314]	0.163
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=3)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3572	p=0.765		p=0.011	
	Publication bias	0.0018	0.0031			0.563
	Points removed	0				

Figure 5. Funnel plot of the meta-analyses of host-specific risk factors for hepatitis A in the mixed (left) and the combined children and susceptible (right) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 3C. Meta-analysis on poor personal hygiene as risk factor for the transmission of hepatitis A – Asia (9 ORs), East Europe (2 OR) and West Europe (1 OR)

Exposure	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Poor personal hygiene (6 stud)	All data	0.573	0.272	12	[0.039 – 1.106]	0.035
	Fixed effects					
	Children	1.173 ^b	0.367	2	[0.454 – 1.892]	0.001
	Mixed	0.271 ^a	0.247	10	[-0.214 – 0.755]	0.273
	Before 2000					0.940
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2099	QE(df=10)		QM(df=2)	
s^2 (residual)	0.2459	p<.0001		p=0.003		
Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0002			0.914	
Points removed	0					

Figure 6. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of poor personal hygiene as a risk factor for hepatitis A infection in the combined mixed children and population

Table 4A. Meta-analysis of pathways related to animal contact for hepatitis A infection by region in the mixed (n=5) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	0.555	0.153	5	[0.255 – 0.855]	<.0001

Table 4B. Meta-analysis of pathways related to animal contact for acquiring hepatitis A infection in the mixed population – Farm (1 OR), Occupational (2 OR), Pets (2 OR) and Wild (1 OR)

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	All animal	0.489	0.138	6	[0.218 – 0.761]	<.0001
(4 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0072	QE(df=5)			
	s^2 (residual)	0.2905	p=0.277			
	Publication bias	0.0001	0.0001			0.183
	Points removed	0				

Figure 6. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of animal contact as risk factor for hepatitis A infection in the mixed population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 5A. Meta-analyses of environmental pathways for acquiring hepatitis A infection by region in the mixed (n=91) and children (n=52) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Africa	1.202	0.210	10	[0.789 – 1.615]	<.0001
East Europe	0.937	0.238	7	[0.471 – 1.404]	<.0001
North America	0.216	0.200	20	[-0.175 – 0.609]	0.278
North Europe	0.592	0.216	8	[0.168 – 1.016]	0.006
South America	0.442	0.126	30	[0.195 – 0.689]	0.001
West Europe	0.379	0.139	16	[0.106 – 0.652]	0.007
Children					
Asia	0.773	0.238	10	[0.307 – 1.239]	0.001
South America	0.537	0.164	37	[0.217 – 0.858]	0.001
Europe	0.148	0.236	5	[-0.315 – 0.610]	0.531

Table 5B. Meta-analyses of environmental pathways for acquiring hepatitis A infection in the mixed (n=81) and children (n=52) population – Africa removed from the mixed population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (32 stud)	All environment	0.481	0.081	81	[0.322 – 0.640]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Day care*	0.659 ^b	0.254	15	[0.162 – 1.157]	0.009
	Drink water	0.197 ^b	0.065	14	[0.069 – 0.323]	0.003
	Farm	0.619 ^c	0.123	8	[0.378 – 0.861]	<.0001
	Playground**	0.566 ^a	0.264	3	[0.048 – 1.084]	0.032
	Rec water	0.076 ^c	0.233	4	[-0.380 – 0.532]	0.745
	Waste***	0.631 ^c	0.124	37	[0.388 – 0.873]	<.0001
	Before 2000					0.616
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0052	QE(df=75)		QM(df=6)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3705	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0000			0.030
	Points removed	0				
Children (13 stud)	All environment	0.495	0.133	52	[0.235 – 0.755]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Day care****	0.518 ^a	0.252	6	[0.024 – 1.013]	0.040
	Drink water	0.596 ^a	0.202	24	[0.201 – 0.991]	0.003
	Farm	0.310 ^a	0.176	3	[-0.035 – 0.654]	0.078
	Waste	0.498 ^a	0.078	19	[0.344 – 0.651]	<.0001
	Before 2000					0.372
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1922	QE(df=48)		QM(df=4)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.4149	p<.0001		p=0.768	
	Publication bias	-0.0004	0.0001			0.001
	Points removed	0				

(*) Working in day care/nursery

(**) Contact with garden and exposure to soil

(***) Contact with human faeces or lack of sanitation facilities

(****) Attending day care facility

Figure 7. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of environmental pathways as risk factors for hepatitis A infection in the mixed (left) and children (right) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 6A. Meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of hepatitis A by region in the combined mixed (n=89), children (n=11) and susceptible (n=10) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All					
Asia	0.561	0.269	21	[0.033 – 1.088]	0.037
East Europe	0.542	0.318	6	[-0.080 – 1.165]	0.088
North America	0.685	0.253	26	[0.188 – 1.181]	0.007
North Europe	0.452	0.460	15	[-0.449 – 1.354]	0.325
South America/Africa	0.165	0.320	7	[-0.463 – 0.793]	0.606
West/South Europe	0.544	0.155	35	[0.239 – 0.849]	0.001

Table 6B. Meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of hepatitis A in the combined mixed (n=87), children (n=6) and susceptible (n=10) population – South America/Africa removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All	Fixed effects					
(31 stud)	Children	1.163 ^b	0.441	6	[0.299 – 2.027]	0.008
	Mixed	0.570 ^a	0.118	87	[0.340 – 0.800]	<.0001
	Susceptible	0.587 ^a	0.323	10	[-0.046 – 1.220]	0.069
	Before 2000					0.434
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2132	QE(df=100)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.7370	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0000			0.914
	Points removed	0				

Figure 8. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of hepatitis A in the combined mixed, children and susceptible population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 7A. Meta-analyses of food pathways for acquiring hepatitis A infection by geographical region in the mixed (n=35) and children (n=11) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	0.906	0.370	8	[0.181 – 1.631]	0.014
North Europe	0.196	0.514	6	[-0.812 – 1.203]	0.704
West Europe	0.796	0.230	21	[0.344 – 1.247]	0.001
Children					
North America	1.935	0.163	7	[1.615 – 2.255]	<.0001
South America	0.404	0.217	2	[-0.021 – 0.829]	0.063
S-W Europe	0.285	0.326	2	[-0.354 – 0.924]	0.382

Table 7B. Meta-analyses of food pathways for acquiring hepatitis A infection in the mixed (n=35) and children (n=11) population – no geographical region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	All foods	0.750	0.194	35	[0.369 – 1.131]	<.0001
(13 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Composite*	0.526 ^a	0.245	3	[0.045 – 1.007]	0.032
	Dairy	0.394 ^a	0.211	2	[-0.021 – 0.808]	0.063
	Produce	1.057 ^b	0.324	3	[0.422 – 1.693]	0.001
	Seafood	0.709 ^a	0.247	26	[0.225 – 1.195]	0.004
	Before 2000					0.467
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0026	QE(df=30)		QM(df=4)	
	s^2 (residual)	1.4359	p<.0001		p=0.001	
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0001			0.896
	Points removed	0				
Children	All foods	0.734	0.335	11	[0.077 – 1.391]	0.028
(5 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Beverages**	0.692 ^a	0.229	4	[0.242 – 1.141]	0.003
	Composite***	2.065 ^b	0.314	3	[1.449 – 2.681]	<.0001
	Produce	1.928 ^b	0.393	2	[1.157 – 2.698]	<.0001
	Seafood	0.302 ^a	0.366	2	[-0.415 – 1.019]	0.408
	Before 2000					ND

Random effects			
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0335	QE(df=7)	QM(df=4)
s^2 (residual)	0.2524	p=0.185	p<.0001
Publication bias	-0.0011	0.0012	0.341
Points removed	0		

- (*) Non-specific food: Seafood/meat/other raw products and meals prepared outside the home
(**) Bottled water, mineral water and ice
(***) Non-specific food: From street vendor/taco stand and “salsa” consumed on trip

Figure 9. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of food pathways for acquiring hepatitis A infection in the mixed (left) and children (right) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 8A. Meta-analysis of seafood consumption pathways for acquiring hepatitis A infection by geographical region in the combined mixed (n=26) and children (n=2) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	0.908	0.788	2	[-0.636 – 2.451]	0.249
North Europe	0.218	0.628	5	[-1.012 – 1.448]	0.729
West Europe	0.807	0.263	21	[0.293 – 1.322]	0.002

Table 8B. Meta-analysis of seafood consumption pathways for acquiring hepatitis A infection in the combined mixed (n=26) and children (n=2) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
(13 stud)	Crustaceans	-0.032 ^a	0.122	3	[-0.270 – 0.207]	0.795
	Molluscs*	0.918 ^b	0.301	20	[0.328 – 1.507]	0.002
	Undefined**	1.980 ^c	0.162	5	[1.663 – 2.296]	<.0001
	Before 2000					0.376
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.9883	QE(df=25)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	1.1961	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0001			0.678
	Points removed	0				

(*) Comprises mussels, oysters, clams, sea shells and (raw shellfish
 (**) Any seafood and raw seafood

Figure 10. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of seafood consumption pathways for acquiring hepatitis A infection in the combined mixed and susceptible population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 10B. Meta-analysis of produce consumption pathways for acquiring hepatitis A infection in the combined mixed (n=3) and children (n=2) population (2 ORs from Asia, 2 ORs from NorthAmerica and 1 OR from Western Europe)

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (3 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Vegetables	1.026	0.599	5	[-0.146 – 2.199]	0.086
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.9841	QE(df=4)			
	s^2 (residual)	0.9607	p<.0001			
	Publication bias	-0.0092	0.0016			<.0001
	Points removed	0				

Figure 11. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of produce consumption pathways for acquiring hepatitis A infection in the combined mixed and children population

Table 11A. Meta-analysis of composite food consumption pathways for acquiring hepatitis A infection by geographical region in the combined mixed (n=3) and children (n=3) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	0.587	0.224	3	[0.148 – 1.027]	0.009
North America	2.289	0.339	3	[1.624 – 2.953]	<.0001

Table 11B. Meta-analysis of composite food consumption pathways for acquiring hepatitis A infection in the combined mixed (n=3) and children (n=3) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
(3 stud)	Dishes*	1.266 ^a	0.473	4	[0.340 – 2.193]	0.007
	Fast-food**	2.320 ^b	0.330	2	[1.673 – 2.968]	<.0001
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.5769	QE(df=4)		QM(df=2)	
	s ² (residual)	0.6137	p<.0001		p=0.067	
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0003			0.685
	Points removed	0				

(*) Non-specific dish outside home, seafood/meat/raw products and salsa consumed on trip
 (**) Children eating at street vendor/taco stand.

Figure 12. Funnel plots of the meta-analysis of composite food consumption pathways for acquiring hepatitis A infection in the combined mixed and children population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Figure 13. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on the possible person-to-person pathways of transmission of hepatitis A in the mixed population (n=89) ordered by country

Figure 14. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on the possible person-to-person pathways of transmission of hepatitis A in children (n=11) and the susceptible population (n=10) ordered by country

Figure 15. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on drinking water as a source of hepatitis A infection in children (n=24) and the mixed population (n=18) ordered by country

Figure 16. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on seafood as source of hepatitis A infection in the distinct populations (n=68) ordered by type of seafood

The main results from the meta-analyses on risk factors and pathways of exposure were compiled by means of two forest plots: the first forest plot (Figure 17) was designed for comparing among the *global* risk categories as potential determinants of hepatitis A infection in the mixed and children populations; and the other (Figure 18) for comparing among the *disaggregated* risk categories and specific pathways of exposure for the mixed and children populations. To visually distinguish the most important routes of transmission, the pooled ORs listed in the forest plots were ranked by mean's decreasing order, and to assess the reliability in the pooled ORs, the number of ORs used in the computations were displayed.

Among the global categories (Figure 17), the most important risk factors for hepatitis A infection in the mixed population were travel (overall OR=3.15; 95% CI: 2.36 – 4.19), host-specific risk factors (overall OR=2.20; 95% CI: 1.34 – 3.61) and the overall food pathways (overall OR=2.12; 95% CI: 1.45 – 3.10), although the latter was mainly represented by seafood (overall OR=2.03; 95% CI: 1.25 – 3.30). In children, the top two global risk factors were host-specific (overall 3.96; 95% CI: 1.54 – 10.14) and person-to-person contagion (overall OR=3.20; 95% CI: 1.35 – 7.59). Travel (overall OR=2.09; 95% CI: 1.33 – 3.28) was as significant a source of hepatitis A in children as the overall food pathways (overall OR=2.08; 95% CI: 1.08 – 4.02). However, person-to-person transmission in the mixed (overall OR=1.77; 95% CI: 1.40 – 2.22) and the susceptible population (overall OR=1.80; 95% CI: 0.96 – 3.39), was not as a strong source of disease as it was in children. Among the

routes of exposure having sufficient data for meta-analysis, both the global animal contact pathways (overall OR=1.63; 95% CI: 1.24 – 2.14 in the mixed population) and the global environmental pathways (overall OR=1.61; 95% CI: 1.38 – 1.90 in the mixed population; and overall OR=1.64; 95% CI: 1.26 – 2.13 in children) bore the lowest risk of acquiring of hepatitis A infection.

Comparing among the disaggregated pathways of exposure to hepatitis A (Figure 18), food vehicles such as non-specific seafood (overall OR=7.24; 95% CI: 5.28 – 9.93 in the mixed population) and eating meals from street vendor (overall OR=7.89; 95% CI: 4.26 – 14.60 in children) turned out to pose the greatest risk of infection. In the mixed population, international travel was the second most important source of hepatitis A (overall OR=4.26; 95% CI: 2.70 – 6.74), followed by the consumption of vegetables (overall OR=2.79; 95% CI: 0.86 – 9.02). Suffering from other medical conditions (overall OR=2.65; 95% CI: 1.52 – 4.62) was as important a risk factor for acquiring hepatitis A infection as the consumption of molluscs (overall OR=2.50; 95% CI: 1.39 – 4.51) and domestic travel (overall OR=2.33; 95% CI: 1.45 – 3.73). Interestingly, working in day care/nursery (overall OR=1.93; 95% CI: 1.18 – 3.18) bore a level of risk comparable to those of being exposed to waste, sewage or lack of sanitation (overall OR=1.88; 95% CI: 1.47 – 2.39) and living on a farm (overall OR=1.86; 95% CI: 1.46 – 2.37) in the mixed population. Keeping poor personal hygiene (overall OR=1.77; 95% CI: 1.04 – 3.02) turned out to be as important a source of hepatitis A as person-to-person contagion (overall OR=1.77; 95% CI: 1.40 – 2.22). Other significant routes of transmission of hepatitis A in the mixed population were contact with garden and soil (overall OR=1.76; 95% CI: 1.05 – 2.95), consumption of non-specific seafood/meat outside the home (overall OR=1.69; 95% CI: 1.05 – 2.74) and drinking untreated water (overall OR=1.22; 95% CI: 1.07 – 1.38), while minor (or not statistically proven) factors for acquiring the disease were suffering from a chronic disease (overall OR=1.48; 95% CI: 0.76 – 2.89), exposure to recreational water (overall OR=1.08; 95% CI: 0.68 – 1.70) and consumption of crustaceans (overall OR=0.97; 95% CI: 0.76 – 1.23).

In children, as opposed to the mixed population, person-to-person contagion (overall OR=3.20; 95% CI: 1.35 – 7.59) was a more important source of hepatitis A infection than international travel (overall OR=2.27; 95% CI: 1.43 – 3.60), whereas suffering from other medical condition bore, at least on average, a similar level of risk (overall OR=2.62; 95% CI: 0.68 – 10.11) as in the mixed population. It was unexpected that drinking bottled water (overall OR=2.00; 95% CI: 1.27 – 3.13) and untreated water (overall OR=1.81; 95% CI: 1.22 – 2.69) posed a comparable level of risk of hepatitis in children. As occurred in the mixed population, children attending day care (overall OR=1.68; 95% CI: 1.02 – 2.75) were at least as exposed to hepatitis A as those exposed to waste, sewage or lack of sanitation (overall OR=1.65; 95% CI: 1.41 – 1.92) and those living on a farm (overall OR=1.36; 95% CI: 0.97 – 1.92). Thus, as a whole, exposures related to day care were strongly associated with hepatitis A infection, be it either adults working at day care centre/nursery or children attending day care.

Figure 17. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring hepatitis A infection for global risk categories, ranked in decreasing order. The global risk categories presented are only those made up of at least n=3 ORs

Figure 18. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring hepatitis A infection in the mixed, children and susceptible population for disaggregated risk categories, ranked in decreasing order. The disaggregated risk categories presented are only those made up of at least n=3 ORs

3.10.3 *Meta-analysis on the effect of handling food on the risk of transmission of hepatitis A*

The only food data partition comprising sufficient data that could support the assessment of the effect of handling was the global seafood partition. Full estimates and a funnel plot of the meta-analysis on the effect of consuming raw seafood is shown in the supplementary Table S1 and Figure S1. For the hepatitis A infection meta-analysis, no data partition had sufficient information on setting; thus, the relative effect of eating food prepared outside the home on the overall association with disease could not be appraised.

Table 12. Meta-analysed effect of handling on base ORs by relevant food class

Food class	Estimate	Mean	2.5 th percentile	97.5 th percentile
Seafood*	OR(Base)	1.693	1.008	2.843
	OR(Raw)/OR(Base)	2.190	1.166	4.112

*Crustaceans (3 ORs), Molluscs (20 ORs) and Undefined (5 ORs)

On meta-analysis, people who ate seafood and became ill with hepatitis A infection were 2.190 times (95% CI: 1.021 – 2.420) more likely to have consumed it without any cooking than those who consumed the same type of food but did not acquire the disease (Table 12). Hence, the practice of “consuming raw seafood” represents on its own a significant risk factor for hepatitis A infection (p=0.015; Table S1).

3.10.4 *Synthesis of the risks associated to poor handling of foods*

Most of the poor food handling habits explored in the primary studies related to hand hygiene (Figure 19). Infrequent or no handwashing before eating was statistically proven to be associated with hepatitis A infection in some case-control studies, with mean ORs ranging from 1.18 to 5.44. No handwashing before food preparation could also represent a risky practice for disease transmission (ORs: 4.68 – 5.46) as well as keeping a dirty kitchen (OR=2.65).

Figure 19. Forest plot of the odds-ratios of acquiring hepatitis A infection associated to poor food handling practices in the mixed and children population

4 Conclusions

4.10 Meta-analysis on risk factors for sporadic hepatitis A infection

- ❖ The outcomes from 78 case-control and cohort studies investigating host-specific factors, travel and pathways of transmission for sporadic hepatitis A infection were meta-analysed within appropriate data partitions, taking into account geographical region and period of study.
- ❖ In the mixed population, the most important *global* risk factors for hepatitis A infection are travel (OR=3.15), host-specific factors (OR=2.20) and consumption of seafood (OR=2.03).
- ❖ In children, the top two *global* risk factors are host-specific factors (OR=3.96) and person-to-person contagion (OR=3.20).

- ❖ Person-to-person transmission in the mixed (OR=1.77) and the susceptible population (OR=1.80) is not as a strong determinant of disease as in children
- ❖ The mixed population is as susceptible to acquiring hepatitis A infection by keeping poor hygiene habits (OR=1.77) as by person-to-person contagion (OR=1.77).
- ❖ The *global* animal contact pathways (OR=1.63 in the mixed population) and the *global* environmental pathways (OR=1.61 in the mixed population; and OR=1.64 in children) pose the lowest risk of acquiring of hepatitis A infection.
- ❖ Among the *disaggregated* pathways of exposure, the top three sources of hepatitis A in the mixed population are: non-specific seafood (OR=7.24), international travel (OR=4.26) and consumption of vegetables (OR=2.79).
- ❖ Having a history of hepatitis/jaundice (OR=2.65) is as highly associated with hepatitis A infection as the consumption of molluscs (OR=2.50) and domestic travel (OR=2.33).
- ❖ The exposures related to day care, be it either adults working at day centre (OR=1.93) or children attending day care (OR=1.68) bear a level of risk comparable to those of being exposed to waste, sewage or lack of sanitation (OR=1.88 in the mixed population; and OR=1.65 in children) or living on a farm (OR=1.86 in the mixed population; and OR=1.36 in children).
- ❖ In children, person-to-person contagion (OR=3.20) is a more important source of hepatitis A infection than international travel (OR=2.27)
- ❖ In some geographical regions, children drinking bottled water (OR=2.00) could be as exposed to hepatitis A infection as drinking untreated water (OR=1.81).
- ❖ Other significant routes of transmission of hepatitis A in the mixed population area: contact with garden and soil (OR=1.76), consumption of non-specific seafood/meat outside the home (OR=1.69) and drinking untreated water (OR=1.22).
- ❖ Minor factors for acquiring the disease are: suffering from a chronic disease (OR=1.48), exposure to recreational water (OR=1.08) and consumption of crustaceans (OR=0.97).
- ❖ Eating *raw* seafood constitutes a risk factor on its own since it increases the odds of acquiring hepatitis A infection by 2.19 times that of consuming seafood.

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5.10 Seventy-eight case-control and cohort primary studies assessing risk factors for hepatitis A infection

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6 Supplementary tables and figures of the effects of handling on the transmission of hepatitis A infection

Table S1. Meta-analysis of the effect of handling on the risk of hepatitis A infection by consumption of crustaceans (n=3), molluscs (n=20) and non-specific seafood (5 ORs) in the combined mixed (n=26), children (n=1) and susceptible (n=1) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All (13 stud)	Base	0.527	0.264	20	[0.008 – 1.045]	0.046
	Raw	0.784	0.322	8	[0.154 – 1.414]	0.015
Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.7222	QE(df=26)			
	s^2 (residual)	1.5175	p<.0001			
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0001			0.836
	Points removed	0				

Figure S1. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis on the effect of handling on the risk of hepatitis A by consumption of seafood